

A QUALITATIVE STUDY ON ORGANIZATIONAL CHALLENGES CONTRIBUTING TO OCCUPATIONAL BURNOUT AMONG FRONTLINE HOTEL EMPLOYEES IN PUNJAB PROVINCE, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Frontline hotel employees in Pakistan faced very high burnout rates, leading to increased intentions to leave. The main factors contributing to emotional exhaustion and feelings of depolarization were linked to various managerial issues that foster a sense of non-accomplishment among employees. Using a qualitative research approach, the study collected subjective responses from employees working in Punjab's hospitality industry. The findings revealed five themes: excessive working conditions, a polarized organizational structure, and interpersonal conflicts with colleagues, and rude customer behavior. In conclusion, working conditions in Multan's hospitality industry are less demanding than those in Lahore. The common challenges faced by hospitality in both areas were worsened by neglecting employees' rights, prioritizing customer satisfaction, and undermining employees' financial interests. This led to conflicting relationships among employees, resulting in feelings of exclusion, non-acceptance, and mistrust. Implementing management strategies—such as rotating shifts, offering performance-based incentives, enforcing a zero-tolerance policy for insulting and harassing employees, and establishing a code of conduct to protect employee rights—can help reduce their burnout.

INTRODUCTION

Occupational burnout, also referred to as employee burnout, has become a widespread global issue with numerous challenges (Ayachit & Chitta, 2022). International data estimates that the economic cost of employee burnout reaches \$300 billion USD (Ali et al., 2022). Workers in the hospitality industry report feeling emotionally drained and struggling to adapt to their roles. They have tried taking sick leave but show little enthusiasm for their careers (McGeary & McGeary, 2012). Earlier research also indicates that hospitality workers face various socio-cultural and managerial hurdles, which can lead to emotional detachment and

feelings of underachievement, ultimately prompting them to consider leaving their jobs (Dutta, 2024; Kumar et al., 2024). Factors such as heavy workloads assigned by managers, unpredictable business conditions that require overtime, diverse responsibilities, and high stress levels all significantly contribute to job burnout. Stressful work environments are significant factors affecting both the economic and social aspects of the hospitality industry (Nisar et al., 2021).

Burnout is not solely an individual problem; it is also shaped by organizational leadership. Managers' behavior toward staff and their

instructions regarding customer service and scheduling are critical factors contributing to employees' emotional exhaustion (Amankwaa et al., 2022). Researchers from Sociology, Psychology, and Management have examined work-related factors that lead to burnout. Evidence indicates that employees with low well-being and those facing workplace stressors are more vulnerable to burnout (Ullah et al., 2025; Wong et al., 2025). The study by Shi et al. (2021) highlighted that resilience explains how employees adapt to situations through accommodation and assimilation. While coping strategies can sometimes be effective, employees still face various emotional challenges that hinder their full integration into the workplace. The hospitality industry relies on both domestic and international tourism, economic growth, and rising consumer wealth. It extends beyond luxury business travel to include various leisure and resort experiences (Ghani et al., 2022). However, customers dining at restaurants—whether for dinner, lunch, high tea, breakfast, or other meals—remain a concern for researchers (Gordon & Adler, 2022). Over the past decade, a key challenge for hotel staff has been their inability to deliver fast, high-quality service to guests. The industry aims to enhance service quality and increase customer satisfaction (Ali et al., 2021; Kumar et al., 2024). In this context, frontline hotel workers (receptionists, waiters, housekeepers) experience higher burnout rates than back-office staff because of direct guest interactions. Burnout among hotel employees can be divided into three main areas: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. Emotional exhaustion means feeling drained after long periods of work. Depersonalization involves detachment and negative attitudes toward guests and colleagues. Feelings of being undervalued and unrecognized are also linked to decreased personal achievement (Gitau et al., 2024; Koniari, 2025).

Sociologists, psychologists, and management analysts are concerned about the challenges hotel employees face during their shifts. A key problem is how employees interact with colleagues, guests, and management. To address this, hotel staff face several challenges in fulfilling their responsibilities, such as managerial polarization, low customer

satisfaction, conflicts among colleagues, manager dominance, long working hours, and unfair task distribution by upper management (Hu et al., 2022). These issues have led to emotional exhaustion and polarization among hotel employees. As a result, burnout occurs due to feelings of low achievement and motivation at work. As stress and emotional fatigue increase, employees' intentions to leave their jobs also rise, especially when they feel unappreciated or unmotivated. Additionally, nepotism, favoritism, and cliques formed by managers and staff have contributed to negative behaviours among hotel employees (Li et al., 2025).

1. Conceptual model grounded in the theoretical foundations

Building on earlier theoretical foundations, the authors developed the current conceptual framework to illustrate how organizational factors contribute to burnout among frontline hotel employees in Punjab province, Pakistan.

1.1. Job-Demand Resources (JD-R) Theory

The Job-Demand Resources theory was introduced by Demerouti, Bakker, Nachreiner, and Schaufeli in 2001. It explains how job characteristics influence employee well-being and performance. The theory highlights that various factors, such as heavy workloads, tight deadlines, insufficient social support, managerial incompetence, and a lack of autonomy, can lead to emotional and psychological problems among employees, potentially resulting in workplace disengagement. The three main elements of job burnout are job demands, job resources, and personal resources, which help buffer the adverse effects of job stressors and promote positive outcomes. Specifically, the framework emphasizes the significant job demands associated with both physical and psychological costs. Physical demands include heavy workloads, long working hours, and physical exhaustion. Psychological demands involve time pressure, emotional strain, and cognitive overload. Social demands, such as conflicts with colleagues and inadequate managerial support, also contribute to emotional exhaustion. Employees use available resources to mitigate the adverse effects of workplace stress and burnout. To combat emotional exhaustion and feelings of

personal inadequacy, employees rely on social support from colleagues and management, as well as feedback, including informational, consistent, and evaluative comments. The theory also highlights that personal resources, such as self-efficacy, optimism, and resilience, are essential for employees to counter occupational burnout and reduce their intention to resign. Recent research in Malaysia (Ahmed Nazim et al., 2024), China (Zhong, 2025), and Pakistan (Naveed & Qamar Zia, 2024) has also applied this theory within the hospitality industry.

The conceptual framework of this study is based on a theoretical model that offers a structured view to clarify the research question. Additionally, this framework includes key concepts identified through interviews conducted during the study. Building on these foundations, the framework was developed by applying the theories discussed earlier in this research. Support for the Job-Demand-Resources theory comes from various job characteristics across social, psychological, emotional, managerial, and economic areas that influence employee satisfaction and performance during work hours in the hotel industry. Furthermore, the study shows that when hotel employees' job resources do not meet their job demands, they are more likely to experience emotional exhaustion.

2. Methods and Materials

2.1. Research Design

A qualitative research design was employed to examine hotel employees' subjective responses to the primary occupational challenges that contributed to their burnout. The contextual relevance of the responses will highlight differences in participants' personal life experiences across the two geographically distinct contexts of the study.

2.2. Study site and recruitment of participants

The study was conducted among employees at six reputable hotels, with three located in Lahore and three in Multan. These employees worked for at least 12 hours per day during their shifts. This demanding schedule involved continuous work without breaks, including serving food, washing dishes, ensuring food quality, managing

guest complaints, and addressing food-related issues.

The two geographic regions exhibit differences in their cultural and management practices. Both are acknowledged for their contributions to the hospitality and tourism industries. While clear distinctions exist in food culture, social interactions, managerial behavior, and professional experiences, employees still face common challenges in the hospitality sector. The subjective responses from these areas differ, highlighting the need for further identification and analysis of the participants involved.

The inclusion criteria for hotel employees in the study are as follows: 1) employed in the industry within the past 12 months; 2) performing various tasks such as front desk duties, food and beverage service, and housekeeping, among others; 3) having at least two years of experience in the same field, including different hotel roles; 4) being at least 25 years old to meet experience requirements; and 5) willing to participate in the research.

2.3. Sample selection

The sample size was determined once responses began to repeat, indicating data saturation. The participating employees included $n_1 = 8$ from Hotel-1, $n_2 = 10$ from Hotel-2, and $n_3 = 12$ from Hotel-3, totaling $N = 30$ hotel employees from Lahore. Additionally, hotel employees from Multan included $n_1 = 7$ from Hotel-1, $n_2 = 9$ from Hotel-2, and $n_3 = 11$ from Hotel-3, for a total of $N = 27$. Participants were selected using purposive sampling. In this method, hotel employees who met the inclusion criteria were chosen to meet the study's objectives. The researchers emphasized careful documentation of the sampling process to ensure transparency, rigor, and the validity of the research.

2.4. Research technique

The main goal of this research was to understand individual experiences and analyze key challenges faced by hotel employees that contribute to workplace burnout. In this context, the primary aim was to provide insights into this sensitive issue, which is known to cause emotional exhaustion among staff. Based on these reasons, the researchers conducted in-

depth interviews to gather detailed, context-specific data from two regions. This approach also encourages the shared creation of knowledge between interviewers and interviewees. For the interviews, the researchers assigned two interviewers, each a Ph.D. scholar with at least five years of experience in this field. Typically, an interview lasted between 45-60 minutes.

2.5. Tool for data collection

The interview guide served as a data-collection tool. It ensured consistency and flexibility while focusing on different aspects of the study. The researchers designed the instrument to act as a roadmap for thoroughly exploring the subject under investigation. The structure of the interview guide is outlined in the following sections: Section 1 covers demographic and background information, including age, gender, family type, family size, years of experience in the hotel industry, casual working hours, shifts within the hotel (peak or casual timings), and frequency of direct interaction with guests. Section 2 discusses significant organizational challenges, including excessive working hours and conditions, polarized and political structures, interpersonal conflicts, strained relationships with colleagues, insufficient financial incentives, and rude customer behavior. Section 3 examines burnout among hotel employees, including emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and a lack of personal achievement. Section 4 offers recommendations to reduce burnout among hotel staff.

2.6. Data analysis

The data was analyzed using thematic analysis. To ensure accuracy and thoroughness, detailed responses, including rich descriptions and speech fillers, were included. The subsequent interviews were transcribed verbatim. Then, the codes were systematically developed and

grouped into deductive and inductive categories. Deductive codes were based on existing literature, the conceptual framework, and the instrumentation. In contrast, inductive codes were derived from the interviews and primary data collected from hotel employees about their perspectives on the recent exploration. Researchers formulated and organized theoretical constructs into themes, then reviewed and refined them to accurately reflect participants' experiences of emotional exhaustion and lack of personal accomplishment. After review, overlapping codes and sub-themes were merged, split, or discarded. The final themes were identified and labelled based on their relevance to the research questions, ensuring a systematic and rigorous analysis process.

2.7. Ethical considerations

Given the sensitivity and privacy concerns of hotel employees regarding their emotional exhaustion, this study incorporated ethical considerations. First, informed consent was obtained from participating hotel employees who agreed to take part in the research. The consent form clearly described the study's goals. Participants were also assured they could withdraw at any time. Trustworthiness was a key focus, directly impacting the integrity of the research findings. The credibility of the results was preserved by accurately representing the experiences of frontline hotel staff concerning organizational challenges that contributed to their emotional exhaustion. Data was collected through transcripts and translated documents. Additionally, confirmability was ensured by avoiding data bias, with responses recorded exactly as given without alteration. Finally, transferability was addressed by considering cultural and organizational differences between the two settings to ensure the findings could be relevant elsewhere.

Fig. 1: Methodological demonstration of the occupational challenges impacting occupational burnout among hotel employees in Lahore and Multan (Punjab)

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive analysis

The descriptive analysis indicated that participants' ages ranged from 22 to 38 years. Of the 30 hotel employees from Lahore (Upper Punjab), 18 were men and 12 were women. The gender distribution among hotel employees in Multan was 20 men and 7 women. Female employees in both groups mostly held roles such as receptionists and front desk staff, responsible for managing busy periods like high tea, breakfast, lunch, and dinner buffets. The employees interviewed generally worked 8 to 12 hours daily, with a short lunch break of 15 to 20 minutes. During busy times, known as high tea, the workload increased considerably—especially from 3:30 p.m. to 6:00 p.m. at four hotels and from 4:00 p.m. to 6:00 p.m. in the remaining two hotels. Regarding family arrangements, most employees follow family systems throughout both summer and winter seasons, with 18 of the 27 employees being married and living in extended or joint family setups. Only two married hotel employees live in nuclear families. In both research locations, unmarried employees said their primary motivation for working was to save money for

future marriages. Demographically, male employees expressed plans to leave their jobs due to perceived limited prospects, lack of respect, or loss of dignity. Female employees reported experiencing harassment from customers, leading them to consider resigning in the future.

3.2. Thematic analysis

Following interviews with hotel staff, five main themes were identified: excessive workload, a divided organizational structure, and interpersonal conflicts with colleagues, and rude customer behavior.

3.2.1. Excessive working conditions

Data from hotel employees in Lahore indicate that they face harsh working conditions characterized by strict rules and regulations. The leading causes of emotional exhaustion among workers include poorly communicated and irregular work schedules. During interviews, employees reported that their managers enforce strict compliance and do not accept excuses for changing duties. Managers tell them to meet demanding schedules with a positive attitude and to follow customer instructions carefully. A

group of sixteen hotel employees from Lahore introduced the term “flipping the time to become double,” explaining that, although they work their required hours, unpredictable shifts and heavy job demands contribute significantly to burnout among hotel staff. The interviews also showed that employees feel divided and still lack a sense of personal achievement because they do not receive recognition for their extra hours. The interviews revealed that employees who previously worked eight hours a day on regular shifts felt healthier physically, emotionally, and socially. However, the emerging culture of busy breakfast, lunch, and dinner buffets, along with high tea times, long hours, late-night duties, and sudden shift changes, is a key factor behind the emotional burnout of employees in upper Punjab. Supporting this view, an employee from Hotel-2 in Lahore explained that;

Extended working hours are manageable; however, inconsistent shifts and new buffet hours have led to burnout. As a result, I am considering resigning from this position.

Transcriptions from Multan indicate that the heavy workload is linked to new cultural practices, such as breakfast timings from 8:00 am to 12:00 pm, high tea timings (3:00 pm to 5:30 pm for the first slot, 5:30 pm to 7:00 pm for the second), as well as lunch deals from 12:00 pm to 4:00 pm and dinner buffets from 8:00 pm to 11:30 pm. During these times, employees are not allowed to leave the dining area, even for a moment. This demanding schedule and workload have caused employees to describe their behavior as operating “like a robot/machine.” Additionally, employees believe their excessive workload results from multiple factors contributing to burnout, including: 1) ongoing instructions and complaints from management about guest service; 2) directives to avoid taking breaks, including restrictions on restroom use, because guests need attention; 3) overtime that harms physical and mental health through sleep deprivation and domestic conflicts; and 4) irregular shifts, including weekends. An employee with 11 years of experience at Hotel-2 in Multan revealed that;

Although I have been promoted to senior waiter, I still work long hours, take on unexpected

responsibilities, and sacrifice family time, leaving me emotionally drained and unfulfilled.

3.2.2. Polarized organizational structure

The transcriptions showed that hierarchical structures in Lahore result in a strict top-down management style, with the hotel manager essentially controlling decision-making. Employees said that this uneven distribution of power encourages favoritism and nepotism, which, in turn, motivates employees to work harder. Staff burnout increases when task assignments create competition and mistrust. Interviews indicated that all decisions are made by upper management, who aim to strengthen this political culture. Participants also shared that managers use promotions, rewards, and appreciation based on favoritism rather than loyalty, effort, or performance. They noted feeling emotionally and physically exhausted when tasks are poorly managed. Employees argued that avoiding politics would be helpful, but hotel management prefers to keep the current political culture. They also revealed that employees whom managers favor—the “apple of managers' eyes”—have created this worsened political environment, leading to burnout and thoughts of leaving among other employees. Ironically, many of these favoured employees are often responsible for fostering this divided culture. When the interviewer asked why employees did not report these issues, a standard answer was that if they spoke the truth, they would be punished and fired. In response, the employee working at Hotel-1 in Lahore argued that;

Employees who focus on their work and avoid flattery often face polarization. I was also not the manager's preferred employee, which prevented me from ever advancing to a better position.

Interviews from Multan demonstrated that factors fueling the polarized culture include a lack of teamwork, communication issues, and unfair treatment by management. A 25-year-old female front desk worker at Hotel-2 explained that favoritism and nepotism—such as small gifts, flattery, and buttering up—by some hotel employees toward the manager foster feelings of polarization. Additionally, emotional exhaustion increases when senior employees tend to group and scapegoat junior or opposing staff. The data indicated that abusive language,

mocking, name-calling, and facial gestures are the main reasons reported for fueling a political atmosphere within the hotel environment. Consensus showed that polarized cultures in hotels often result in favoritism, bullying, and the formation of cliques targeting specific employees. Submissive workers become caught in this political environment and usually do not receive the recognition they deserve. Without acknowledgment or rewards for their efforts, these employees are more likely to experience burnout and consider leaving their jobs. The data also revealed that employees feel disempowered and demotivated because they see no promising future. They expressed a desire to gain experience and attain respected positions within the hotel. Conversely, participants argued that a politically and culturally biased environment fosters segregation among staff, hinders workplace productivity, and exacerbates employee burnout. Transcripts revealed that hotel employees feel demotivated due to a political divide regarding the allocation, appreciation, and reporting of tasks to the manager. Supporting these points, an employee who has worked at Hotel-A of Multan for the past 10 years confirmed the polarized and segregated culture in the hotels and argued that; *Even within a participative organizational structure, staff politics caused polarization and division. For me, feelings of burnout are exacerbated by a lack of recognition, leading to a sense of being undervalued and unappreciated.*

3.2.3. Interpersonal conflicts with colleagues

Data from employees working in Lahore hotels shows that uneven workload distribution is the main cause of staff conflicts. It was reported that employees considered “the apple of the manager's eye” received more manageable tasks, while others carried heavier loads. This overburdens some workers and fosters jealousy and hostility toward favoured colleagues. Additionally, the power gap between managers and new employees is a key source of conflict among staff. Five senior employees at Hotel-2 in Lahore reported ongoing disputes, citing feelings of being undervalued and excluded as the main reasons for disagreements with others. Jealousy and mistrust increase when roles overlap, especially during busy periods, leading to various arguments. The collective feedback

from interviews at Hotel-3 focused on misunderstandings and indirect communication among staff. This issue was linked to employees' rural backgrounds, which led them to be bullied, ignored, and excluded by managers and colleagues. Employees also reported burnout due to their workloads when managers and senior staff fail to use conflict resolution techniques. Another recurring point was that some managers intentionally create conflicts to assert dominance over employees. Transcripts reveal that factors such as manager favoritism toward certain employees, a lack of rotation policies for junior staff, and abusive gestures from colleagues and customers contributed to negative group dynamics, leading to conflicts among staff. In validation, an employee from Hotel-3, who faced constant conflict from colleagues and managers and planned to resign from the job, argued that;

The primary causes of conflict among employees include managers' uneven workload distribution, often due to favoritism, and the lack of rotation in duty schedules. The conflict worsened when employees experienced abusive behavior from their colleagues because of the toxic work environment.

Interviews revealed that the organizational environment in hotels of Multan mainly focuses on professional jealousy and politics among employees. The consensus was that managers aim to maintain the political status quo among staff. Another reported cause of polarization and a lack of professional growth was poor communication, including rude language, inappropriate facial expressions, minor scolding, unclear duty schedules, and ineffective communication methods. These issues led to emotional disengagement and feelings of personal inadequacy. Despite these communication problems, the primary sources of conflict were (i) unfair workload distribution, (ii) favoritism toward certain employees—especially those who flatter management or gossip to sustain the organizational political culture—and (iii) resentment toward team members who avoid their assigned tasks. Additionally, the food culture in Multan shows that employees often feel emotionally drained because managers discriminate against them based on caste, language, and education. Interviews also revealed that managers criticized employees' accents and insulted them in front of

customers, while praising more educated colleagues—even those with native accents. One employee with thirteen years of experience at Hotel-2 in Multan shared that he felt burnt out and wanted to quit due to ongoing conflicts with colleagues.

Conflicts between employees are common. However, the leading causes of these conflicts include personality differences, language barriers, and management's political tactics to keep staff divided. So, how can we prevent burnout and protect our well-being at work?

3.2.4. Rude behavior of the customers

Recent data from Lahore indicate that customers' rude behavior toward hotel staff primarily results from their heightened expectations for service, hospitality, and hotel ambiance. Other common issues include delays in service after orders are placed, problems with table availability, occasional misunderstandings leading to incorrect dishes being served, and difficulties overcoming language barriers. Staff often experience emotional exhaustion when dealing with self-centered customers who believe that paying large bills gives them authority over hotel staff. Interviews also revealed that customers from the elite class view employees as mere servants and do not deserve respectful treatment. Two participants from Hotel-3 in Lahore offered a different perspective, arguing that customers are not rude but rather demanding. The burnout of hotel employees often leads to emotional collapse when they are subjected to training that expects them to cater to customers, who are considered the kings of a hotel; therefore, managers and owners aim to please them. To do so, they sacrifice the dignity and self-respect of ordinary hotel employees. Supporting this, a hotel employee, who was considering resigning due to ongoing emotional exhaustion and feelings of a lack of achievement, argued that;

I have personally noticed that customers sometimes treat employees with harsh facial expressions and abusive language. So how can an employee feel normal and avoid emotional exhaustion at work?

Transcriptions from hotel employees in Multan revealed that demanding, rude, and impatient customer behavior is the leading cause of employee burnout. Participants mentioned that

although they are expected to serve customers with a smile, good manners, hospitality, and politeness, customers often treat them like their “personal servants” [Zaati Mulazim]. It was also noted that rude customer conduct significantly increases stress, anxiety, and burnout at work. Most employees agree that such rude behavior is common during peak hours. During these times, many customers seek quick attention and fast service. One employee working during high tea at the hotel confirmed experiencing verbal abuse several times because customers do not see these employees as human beings. Interviews also revealed that customers often speak harshly, display rude facial expressions, use insulting words (such as “blind,” “mad,” “insolent”), and even shout at staff. Common insults include “aandhe ho kia,” “itni dair se bulaya hai,” “jahil,” “batameez,” and “pagal insan itni dair kar di.” Interviews indicated a consensus that customers who had not reserved tables in advance arrived with guests and behaved in an impolite manner toward female staff. In contrast, guests with reservations expressed dissatisfaction with the seating arrangements. From the participants' comments, the primary reasons attributed to the rude behavior of the customers were (i) delays in fulfilling their orders, (ii) ignoring customer instructions, and (iii) dismissing customer complaints and demands. As evidence of these facts, an employee who has worked at Hotel-1 for the past seven years said and felt the depolarization, and emotional collapse reported that;

From my professional experience, I can confidently say that rude, impolite, and discourteous customer behavior reduces employee motivation and emotional well-being.

4. Discussion

The organizational challenges in the hospitality industry that lead to employee burnout remain a global issue (Giousmpasoglou, 2024). Previous research in Pakistan confirms that problems such as heavy workloads, work-life balance, customer behavior, managerial dominance, co-worker conflicts, and a polarized organizational structure contribute to emotional exhaustion among hospitality workers (Murtza et al., 2022). Additionally, a study in Portugal involving frontline and backstage hotel staff found that

role conflict is the leading cause of their emotional exhaustion. It also highlights how age and gender influence job satisfaction and employee integration within the hotel industry (Prentice et al., 2025). Consistent with recent research, empirical evidence from Pakistan and China shows that employee empowerment and motivation are vital for organizational success (Nadeem et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2022).

The findings of this study show that employee overwork is the leading cause of burnout among hotel staff in the hospitality industry. Excessive work, including overtime, continuous duties during busy periods, long working hours, and hotel-specific policies on work hours, significantly contribute to employee burnout in the hospitality sector. Supporting these findings, previous research by Ayachit & Chitta (2022); Weerakit et al. (2025) indicated that overwork and overtime lead to stress, anxiety, emotional exhaustion, and intentions to leave among hospitality workers. Additional evidence from Tan et al. (2020) supported the theoretical basis of this study. The Job Demand-Resources theory was employed to investigate how heavy workloads contribute to burnout and turnover intentions among hotel employees. Additionally, a study in Pakistan by Daraz (2024) supports these findings, revealing that during the COVID-19 pandemic, hotel employees in Swat experienced constant stress, anxiety, and burnout due to their job. Employees expressed a desire to quit primarily because of overwork, staffing shortages, and an overly burdensome work system.

The findings of this study showed that managers contributed to organizational polarization among hotel employees. They aimed to maintain the status quo using a divide-and-rule strategy in the hospitality industry. This polarized organizational structure leads to stress, loneliness, isolation, segregation, and emotional exhaustion among hotel employees in the study area. Consistent with this, previous research conducted in Egypt by Shehata et al. (2022) found that organizational politics contributed to burnout among hotel employees. The research also demonstrated that management is responsible for organizational politics, which create political polarization, resulting in stress, anxiety, and a negative perception of their jobs among hotel employees. The other study

conducted by Karatepe (2013) also revealed that organizational politics led to a lack of commitment among hotel employees towards their jobs.

Another key finding of this research is that managers' biased behavior and favoritism are the leading causes of conflict and emotional exhaustion among hotel staff. Supporting this, Shi et al. (2024) found that the hospitality industry faces serious problems with disagreements and strained relationships among hotel employees. As a result, workplace conflicts can demotivate employees and harm their performance. Additionally, a study by Danauské et al. (2023) indicated that conflict in hotels occurs at three levels: between employees, between an employee and a manager, and between an employee and a customer. The study found that all types of conflicts lead to emotional burnout, causing employees to consider quitting their jobs. A further study by Yu et al. (2020) analyzed 36 articles and found that managers often experience abusive supervision, which can become a source of conflict for them. Extending this, studies in Pakistan by Aman Ullah et al. (2024), and Salama et al. (2022) found that favoritism and customer incivility are significant factors contributing to emotional exhaustion among hospitality employees.

This study also reveals that rude customer behavior and disrespect can harm employee performance and contribute to emotional burnout in the hospitality industry. In validation, the earlier empirical study by Yin et al. (2023) also found that customer incivility, abusive language, and facial gestures make employees feel dehumanized and depolarized. Additional evidence from Torres et al. (2017), who surveyed 297 hotel employees, suggested that disrespect, aggression, insulting comments, frustration, and verbal attacks are primary factors contributing to employee burnout and feelings of a lack of achievement. Evidence from Pakistan's hospitality industry, as reported by Shahzad et al. (2023), indicated that four- and five-star hotels are facing significant employee issues, including burnout and intentions to leave. The main reason given was that Pakistani society socializes customers to see hotel employees as their servants. The findings demonstrated that the service-oriented hospitality industry is based on the idea that "the

customer is always right,” with managers believing customers are stakeholders who contribute to employee satisfaction (Nawaz et al., 2020; Sarwar & Muhammad, 2021).

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the hospitality industry offers different contexts for hotel staff, who face various challenges that lead to emotional exhaustion and detachment from their jobs. The study's findings showed that long working hours with insufficient breaks, combined with a fragmented organizational structure, negatively affect employee motivation in hotels in Lahore and Multan. Hotel management in Lahore enforces longer working hours through strict rules and regulations, increasing professional pressure on employees. From the empirical insights, it was clear that upper management often manipulates the political culture to control employees using a strategy of “divide and rule.” This conflict worsens when customers behave rudely toward staff, and managers’ reprimand employees for minor mistakes. The polarized culture is further intensified by the uneven distribution of identity and inclusion, which encourages managers to engage in favoritism and nepotism. The additional factors contributing to the political distancing of certain hotel employees were their inability to receive bonuses, health benefits, or additional reimbursements during peak periods. The financial discrepancies are accompanied by a lack of health benefits, limited opportunities for career progression, and the absence of a tipping culture. The primary source of exclusion and mistrust among employees peaks when they are ignored, bullied, or excluded due to perceived unfair workload distribution, lack of recognition, inadequate appreciation, communication gaps, and being insulted in front of customers. These burnout symptoms affect workers’ well-being and negatively impact their job performance.

6. Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to reduce burnout among employees in the hospitality industry of Lahore and Multan.

1. The hotel staff should be augmented to ensure shift hours are fairly shared among employees in the hospitality industry.
2. Employees who work more efficiently and professionally should be rewarded with bonuses and recognition that motivate them to perform at their best.
3. Managers should avoid favoritism, name-calling, abusive language, and authoritative behavior toward employees to prevent feelings of division and burnout.
4. The owner should correctly assign, value, and report tasks to prevent a culture of politics and segregation among employees.
5. Employees should receive performance-based incentives to motivate them to work more enthusiastically for the hotel's improvement.
6. Managers should avoid fostering a culture of favoritism, flattery, and singling out certain employees because of their limited education or poor customer communication skills.
7. The hotel management should enforce a zero-tolerance policy that protects the rights of hotel employees.

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